

Efficacy of Trigonal Electrofulguration for Women with Antibiotics Recalcitrant Recurrent Urinary Tract Infections

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Abstract

Background: recurrent UTIs represent one of the most common healthcare problems in women with multiple difficulties in treatment due to bacterial resistance to antibiotics and persistent infection in the urinary tract, so we search for alternative management to overcome this problem.

One of the alternatives is the cystoscopic electrofulguration of bladder trigon to eradicate intracellular bacterial communities, which was proposed as one of the causative factors for bacterial persistence in the urinary tract.

Aim of the study: To determine the efficacy of trigonal electrofulguration for women with antibiotics recalcitrant recurrent urinary tract infections including the rate of UTI recurrences, symptomatic improvement, and antibiotic sensitivity of bacteria following EF.

Patients and methods: This study was a prospective interventional study conducted at Al-Kufa Urology Center, Al-sadder Medical City, al-Najaf al-Ashraf, Iraq in the period from December 2021 to October 2024.

A total of 42 women above 15 years were included in this study were diagnosed with RUTI proved by culture and sensitivity do not respond to multiple courses of antibiotics with no other urological abnormalities, and normal upper tract imaging with cystoscopic findings of trigonitis, we did for them trigonal electrofulguration.

Results: Clinical success was recorded in thirty-one (74%) women; 17% were cured and 57% were improved while eleven (26%) patients had clinical failure. No adverse effects were reported by all the patients during the follow-up period.

Conclusion: Cystoscopic electrofulguration is effective and safe in the treatment of antibiotics-recalcitrant recurrent urinary infections. A response rate of 74% with no adverse effects was recorded from our study.

Introduction

Urinary tract infections (UTIs) are common problems, affect men and women of all ages, vary dramatically in their presentation and sequelae, and are among the most frequent reasons for prescribing antibiotics [1]. The overwhelming majority of UTIs contribute to varying levels of morbidity yet rarely progress to life-threatening emergencies. In certain populations, however, UTIs can contribute to significant mortality if undiagnosed and untreated. When bacterial virulence increases or host defense mechanisms decrease, bacterial inoculation, colonization, and urinary tract infection occur [1]. Careful diagnosis and treatment

result in successful resolution of infections in most instances [1]. A better understanding of the pathogenesis of UTIs and the role of host and bacterial factors has improved the ability to identify patients at risk and prevent or minimize sequelae. Recent evidence has proven that urine is not sterile; in many cases, bacteriuria is protective against the development of UTIs [1]. In this era of widespread multidrug-resistant (MDR) bacteria, we mustn't over-diagnose UTIs and expose patients to unnecessary antibiotics [1]. Clinical presentation, in conjunction with analysis of urine samples that are collected properly, must be critically

More Information

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determined before recommending antibiotics for bacteriuria and UTIs [1].

Over half of all women will experience at least one UTI in their lifetime [2], and one study showed that 18% experience at least two additional UTIs within 1 year. [3]. RUTIs have a significant impact on health-related quality of life and are a major contributor to healthcare costs due to sick leave, doctor visits, and antibiotic prescriptions [2,4,5].

UTI is an inflammatory response of the urothelium to bacterial invasion that is usually associated with bacteriuria and pyuria.

Pyuria, the presence of white blood cells (WBCs) in the urine, is generally indicative of infection and/or an inflammatory response of the urothelium to bacteria, stones, an indwelling foreign body, or other conditions that can contribute to pyuria. Bacteriuria without pyuria is generally indicative of bacterial colonization without overt infection of the urinary tract. Pyuria without bacteriuria, or sterile pyuria, warrants further evaluation [1].

Cystitis describes a clinical syndrome of dysuria, frequency, urgency, and occasionally suprapubic pain [1].

Trigonitis is a condition of inflammation of the trigone region of the bladder diagnosed visually during cystoscopy [6].

UTIs may also be defined by their relationship to other UTIs:

A first or isolated infection occurs in an individual who has never had a UTI or has one remote infection from a previous UTI [1].

An unresolved infection has not responded to antimicrobial therapy and is documented to be the same organism with a similar resistance profile [1].

Recurrent infection occurs after documented, successful resolution of an antecedent infection. Consider these two different types of recurrent infection:

1. Reinfection describes a new event associated with the reintroduction of bacteria into the urinary tract [1].
2. Bacterial persistence refers to a recurrent UTI caused by the same bacteria reemerging from a focus within the urinary tract, such as an infectious stone or the prostate [1].

Relapses are frequently used interchangeably. These definitions require careful clinical and bacteriologic assessment and are important because they influence the type and extent of the patient's evaluation and treatment [1].

Methodology

Study Sample

This study was a prospective interventional study conducted at Al-Kufa Urology Center, Al-sadder

Medical City, Al-Najaf Al-ashraf, Iraq in the period from December 2021 to October 2024

A total of 42 patients included in this study were diagnosed with recurrent UTIs. With the failure of multiple courses of antibiotic treatment.

Ethical Consideration

Before collecting any data and intervention, we obtained verbal and written consent from each patient after being informed of the study's objectives. Every patient had the full, absolute right to withdraw at any moment. Patients were assured that the confidentiality of their data was guaranteed throughout the study.

Information regarding demographic data, history, physical examination, laboratory data (including general urine examination, culture, and sensitivity before and after intervention), and imaging, were collected directly from the patients.

Inclusion Criteria

Above 15 years old women with recurrent UTIs do not respond to multiple courses of antibiotics according to c/s for at least 1 year before proceeding to cystoscopy with no other urological abnormalities, and normal upper tract imaging with cystoscopic findings of trigonitis.

Exclusion Criteria

Patients with:

1. voiding dysfunction like neurogenic bladder or incontinence requiring additional procedures at the time of EF such as urethral dilatation, Botox, or deflux bulking agent injection.
2. uncontrolled diabetes.
3. patients with complicating urological conditions that lead them to RUTIs such as chronic intermittent catheterization or Foley's catheters.
4. patients lost from follow-up.

For our study, RUTIs were defined as two UTIs in 6 months or three or more UTIs in 12 months. with at least one documented positive culture in the past year before deciding cystoscopy.

Trigonitis was defined as chronic mucosal inflammation of the trigone region that was diagnosed during cystoscopy. (7)

Diagnostic Cystoscopy

Under general anesthesia or spinal anesthesia, lithotomy position, inspect the genitalia and urethral meatus for any anatomical abnormalities, then we used a 22 Fr. rigid cystoscope with a 30-degree telescopic lens, we started checking the urethra for stricture or any other anatomical anomalies, bladder neck for contracture, ureterocele, or polyps, trigone region for trigonitis (Figure 2.1) (pus pockets, submucosal calcifications, bullies), leukoplakia, ureteric orifices for vesicoureteral reflux features, and rest of the urinary bladder for any abnormalities like growths, diverticula, trabeculation, etc.

Figure 1: Cystoscopic Picture Showing the Typical Features of Trigonitis

Check cystoscope was done by the same specialist urologist or her trainee's physicians and documented by imaging.

Women with RUTIs do not respond to multiple courses of antibiotics for at least one year before cystoscopy with no other urological abnormalities, and normal upper tract imaging with cystoscopic findings of trigonitis, we did for them trigonal electrofulguration at the same session.

Trigonal Electrofulguration Procedure

After finishing the check cystoscope under general or spinal anesthesia, we insert 24 fr. Storz Resectoscope with roller cautery ball at low setting 20 to 40-watt,

electrofulguration of visible lesions in the trigon area between ureteric orifices and bladder neck with special care to avoid electrical heat from reaching to orifices and bladder Neck (picture 2.2.), then insert foley catheter usually 14 fr. for few hrs. and removed before patient discharged home. Patients discharged home on day 0 post-operation on prophylactic antibiotics and local analgesics like phenazopyridine tab to relieve dysuria that may occur during the post-operative period which is self-limited.

EF was done by the same urologist or her trainee physicians.

Figure 2: Cystoscopic View for Trigonal Electrofulguration Procedure

Patients were followed for at least one-year post-EF with 1,3,6,12-month intervals. For recurrent attacks of UTI documented by GUE, urine culture /sensitivity, or antibiotic courses prescribed for symptoms that may indicate UTI.

In our thesis we depend on the number of UTI attacks/year and the Patient's symptoms assessment during attacks of UTI, mainly:

1. dysuria which depends on Description of dysuria discomfort scale: grading extract from Boyarsky score (table 1.) [8];

- 2. frequency and urgency on overactive bladder symptoms score. (OABSS) table 2 [23], and
- 3. suprapubic pain on visual analogue score (VAS) Figure 3 [9].

The outcomes were defined as:

Cure: zero attacks of UTI.

Improvement: Two or less attacks of UTI / yr.

Failure: three or more attacks of UTI / yr.

Table 1.: Description of Dysuria Discomfort Scale: Grading Extract from Boyarsky Score

Degree	Description
0	No symptoms
1	Burning sensation during urination less than 50% of the time
2	Frequent burning sensation during urination, more than 50% of the time
3	Continuous Burning sensation during urination

Table 2: Frequency and Urgency on Overactive Bladder Symptoms Score (OABSS)

Question	Frequency	Score
How many times do you typically urinate from waking in the morning until sleeping at night?	7 or less	0
	8 – 14	1
	15 or more	2
How many times do you typically wake up to urinate from sleeping at night until waking in the morning?	0	0
	1	1
	2	2
	3 or more	3
How often do you have a sudden desire to urinate, which is difficult to defer?	Not at all	0
	Less than once a week	1
	Once a week or more	2
	About once a day	3
	2-4 times a day	4
	5 times a day or more	5

Figure 3: Visual Analog Score (VAS)

Statistical Analysis

Data were processed using Microsoft Excel 2010 and SPSS version 26. Qualitative parameters were expressed as numbers and frequencies while means and standard deviations represented quantitative variables. Qualitative variables were compared using Fisher's exact test and chi-square test while quantitative parameters were compared using paired and unpaired T test. A P-value of less than 0.05 was regarded as significant.

Results

Table 3 entails a general description of forty-two women who were enrolled in the study. Frequencies of different age groups are illustrated in Figure 4.

Table 3: General Description of the Study Population

Parameter	Patients (n=42)
Age (years) Mean (SD)	32.21(12.99)
BMI (kg/m ²) Mean (SD)	25.92(3.84)
Smoking status; n (%)	
Yes	4(9.50%)
No	38(90.50%)
Marital status; n (%)	
Yes	33(78.60%)
No	9(21.40%)
Parity Mean (SD)	2.52(2.17)
Comorbid disease; n (%)	
DM	4(9.52%)
HTN	2(4.76%)
Hormonal drug usage; n (%)	
Yes	11(26.20)
No	31(73.80)
Previous pelvic surgery; n (%)	
Yes	11(26.20)
No	31(73.80)
Bacteria type; n (%)	
Escherichia coli	33(79%)
Klebsiella	3(7%)
Multiple organism	6(14%)
Follow-up duration (months) Mean (SD)	15.66(3.55)

Note: *SD; standard deviation, BMI; body mass index, Comorbid diseases include diabetes mellitus and hypertension, and Hormonal drugs include systemic and local usage.

Figure 4: Histogram Showing Age Distribution in the Study Sample

Figure 5: Clinical Success and Failure Rates of the Electrofulguration

Clinical success was recorded in thirty-one (74%) women; 17% were cured and 57% were improved while eleven (26%) patients had clinical failure as shown in figure 5. No adverse effects were reported by all the patients during the follow-up period.

Compared to women with clinical success, the incidence of post-electrofulguration culture positivity was significantly higher, and mean follow-up was significantly longer in patients with clinical Failure. Other parameters were not significantly different between clinical success and failure groups as shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Comparison of Baseline Parameters between Patients with ≤ Two Urinary Tract Infections per Year and Those with ≥ Three Urinary Tract Infections per Year in the Post-Fulguration Period

Parameter	≤ two UTIs/year (n=31)	≥ three UTIs/year (n=11)	P-value
Age (years) Mean (SD)	32.51(13.65)	31.36(11.50)	0.80
BMI (kg/m ²) Mean (SD)	26.16(3.89)	25.27(3.82)	0.51
Smoking status; n (%)			0.95
Yes	3(10%)	1(9%)	
No	28(90%)	10(91%)	
Marital status; n (%)			0.76
Yes	24(77%)	9(82%)	
No	7(23%)	2(18%)	
Parity Mean (SD)	2.64(2.21)	2.18(2.13)	0.55
Comorbid disease; n (%)			
DM	1(3.23%)	3(27.3%)	0.04
HTN	2(6.45%)	0(0%)	1.00
Hormonal drug usage; n (%)			0.48
Yes	9(71%)	2(18%)	
No	22(29%)	9(82%)	
Previous pelvic surgery; n (%)			0.92
Yes	8(26%)	3(28%)	
No	23(74%)	8(72%)	
Positive post-EF culture; n (%)			0.04
Yes	20(65%)	11(100%)	
No	11(35)	0(0%)	
Bacteria type; n (%)			0.80
Escherichia coli	18(58.1%)	9(82%)	
Klebsiella	1(3.2%)	1(9%)	
Multiple organism	1(3.2%)	1(9%)	
Follow-up duration (months) Mean (SD)	14.87(2.43)	17.90(5.166)	0.01

Electrofulguration resulted in significant differences in urinary symptoms between preoperative and postoperative values in patients with clinical success and those with clinical failure as shown in Table 5 and 6 respectively.

Table 7 shows that patients in failure group even with failed EF have symptomatic improvement parallel to success group.

Table 5: Perioperative Urinary Symptoms Change in the Clinical Success Group

Parameter	≤ two UTIs/year		P-value
	Preoperative	Postoperative	
Pain VAS score Mean (SD)	3.16(2.08)	1.03(1.16)	< 0.0001
Dysuria Boyarsky score Mean (SD)	2.48(0.50)	1.2(0.84)	< 0.0001
Frequency OABSS Mean (SD)	1.58(0.56)	0.83(0.77)	< 0.0001
Urgency OABSS Mean (SD)	1.51(0.96)	0.64(0.60)	< 0.0001

Note: *UTIs; urinary tract infections, VAS; visual analogue scale, SD; standard deviation, OABSS; overactive bladder symptom score, P-value less than 0.05 was regarded significant.

Table 6: Perioperative Urinary Symptoms Change in the Clinical Failure Group

Parameter	≥ three UTIs/year		P-value
	Preoperative	Postoperative	
Pain VAS score Mean (SD)	5.54(2.06)	2.63(1.96)	0.0003
Dysuria Boyarsky score Mean (SD)	2.63(0.50)	1.72(0.90)	0.0016
Frequency OABSS Mean (SD)	1.81(0.40)	1.09(0.70)	0.0004
Urgency OABSS Mean (SD)	1.90(0.53)	1.45(0.82)	0.0162

Note: *UTIs; urinary tract infections, VAS; visual analogue scale, SD; standard deviation, OABSS; overactive bladder symptom score, P-value less than 0.05 was regarded significant.

Table 7: Comparison of Perioperative Urinary Symptoms Change between Patients with ≤ Two Urinary Tract Infections per Year and Those with ≥ Three Urinary Tract Infections per Year

Parameter	≤ two UTIs/year (n=31)	≥ three UTIs/year (n=11)	P-value
Δ Pain VAS score Mean (SD)	2.12(1.87)	2.90(1.75)	0.23
Δ Dysuria Boyarsky score Mean (SD)	1.25(0.92)	0.90(0.70)	0.26
Δ Frequency OABSS Mean (SD)	0.74(0.77)	0.72(0.46)	0.95
Δ Urgency OABSS Mean (SD)	0.87(0.92)	0.45(0.52)	0.16

Note: *UTIs; urinary tract infections, VAS; visual analogue scale, SD; standard deviation, OABSS; overactive bladder symptom score, P-value less than 0.05 was regarded significant.

Discussion

Urinary tract infections affect females more frequently with more than half of women susceptible to suffering an episode at one point during their lifetime [10]. Recurrent infections of the urinary tract, in particular, entail considerable morbidity and impair life quality [11]. Recurrent urinary infections may disrupt sexual life, workability, and social functioning [12]. Extended regimens of low-dose antibiotics have been considered the gold standard option for preventing the recurrences in urinary tract infections [13-15]. however, urinary infections may recur upon

withholding the prophylactic antibiotic [16]. Additionally, antibiotics given for such long periods may increase the risk of provoking resistant organisms [17].

Our study enrolled forty-two women with recurrent urinary infections who were recalcitrant to antibiotics. All women underwent cystoscopic electrofulguration and were followed up for a minimum of twelve months post-electrofulguration. A recent cohort included a comparable number of patients (n=44) as our sample to assess the long-term efficacy of electrofulguration in women with recurrent urinary infections [18]. Also, co-

authors conducted their study on 37 women to analyze the factors affecting the post-electrofulguration recurrence rate of urinary infections [19]. On the contrary, a recent retrospective study, which was performed by [20] and his co-workers, included ninety-five patients. Another study, which analyzed the Cost-effectiveness of electrofulguration in women with recurrent infection of the lower urinary tract, enrolled ninety-three patients [21]. On the other hand, there are series that used a smaller sample size than ours like who studied the association of bladder-indwelled bacteria and post-electrofulguration infection recurrence by analyzing data from thirty-four women [22]. Similarly, and his colleagues assessed the efficacy of electrofulguration in thirty-three women who presented with recurrent urinary infections [23].

The mean age of women in our study was 32.21 years. Recurrent urinary tract infections are mainly a disease of young women [24]. Young age women represent the reproductive age group who are frequently exposed to sexual activity with an increasing chance of contracting a urinary infection [25]. In contrast, the previous series, that studied electrofulguration in patients with recurrent infections of the urinary tract, recruited women of older age [26-28]. This disparity can be explained by the fact that our country (Iraq) comprises mainly of young population with shortages in older age groups for both sexes where women aged fifty-five or older contribute to only a smaller proportion of the total population [29].

Conclusion

According to our research, thirty-one (74%) patients were cured (n=7) or improved (n=24) while eleven women failed to respond to electrofulguration. Even patients who were failed to electrofulguration experienced a significant improvement in urinary symptoms in the postoperative period. ninety women underwent cystoscopic electrofulguration for recurrent infections of the urinary tract. After a median follow-up duration of 4.9 years, the median urinary tract infection rate drops to 0.8 per year. Cure, improvement, and failure were recorded by in fourteen (15%), sixty-nine (73%), and twelve (13%) women respectively. and his colleagues performed electrofulguration in fifty-seven women and found, after an average follow-up period of 2.9 years, that fifteen patients (26.3%) were cured, thirty-seven (65%) patients were improved, and five (8.7%) women were failed to respond. [30] conducted a study on ninety-six women, who had cystoscopic fulguration and followed them up for a median period of 11 years. [31] reported that cure, improvement, and failure were recorded in 72%, 22%, and 6% of women respectively. Moreover, reported that the success rate of electrofulguration was 76% (cure and improvement). Furthermore, showed, in their study on seventy-three women with recurrent infections of the urinary tract,

that the infection-free rate for electrofulguration was 96% and 53% after one and two years respectively [32]. Additionally, electrofulguration was successful in 89% of patients five years' post-procedure.

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